

PROSPECT Drilling and Instrumentation Package: Status and Next Steps for flight on IM-4.

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Introduction:

The PROSPECT package [1] has been defined to address scientific and exploration objectives, with a particular focus on volatiles at the lunar polar regions. Development of the package is underway for accommodation aboard the IM-4 platform of Intuitive Machines selected in the frame of the NASA-CLPS programme. In this context, the launch, flight, landing and operations of PROSPECT will be enabled via this commercial partnership, and in the frame of ESA-NASA cooperation.

Package Definition: PROSPECT consists primarily of a drill & sample acquisition device (ProSEED Drill & Positioner), a sample processing unit (ProSPA Solids Inlet System), an instrumentation suite (ProSPA Analytical Laboratory), and a centralised electrical interface (PROSPECT Control Electronics Unit) [2]. A set of supporting instrumentation is integrated with these units including: drill imaging system, subsurface permittivity sensor, and dedicated temperature sensors. This configuration is developed in the frame of an ESA contract, under the Primeship of Leonardo S.p.A (Italy) – who are also technical responsible for the ProSEED drilling system – and with the key contribution of Open University (UK) as ProSPA instrument responsible.

During the PROSPECT project this team has already implemented development and engineering models of both the drilling system and core elements of the ProSPA instrument, which have supported the establishment of the detailed design.

Baseline Modification: Originally conceived in the frame of a one Earth-year lunar surface phase, changes to the baseline mission have required a rescope of the planned surface activities to achieve the key PROSPECT objectives within a single lunar day of operations.

In mid-2024, NASA have selected Intuitive Machines to fly PROSPECT to a site in the lunar south polar region as part of the NASA-CLPS programme. Since IM's selection, the PROSPECT Team have worked closely with IM's engineering team to consolidate PROSPECT physical and operational interfaces, both of the flight and of the ground segment. This work is ongoing, in parallel to the build up of the PROSPECT qualification and flight model hardware & software.

PROSPECT Science Team: Supporting ESA and the industrial consortium is a team of scientists with a key role in both the future exploitation of PROSPECT data to achieve its objectives, and in the scientific aspects of the package development [3]

including the operations concept. The science team, providing in-depth expertise on science objectives addressed by PROSPECT and the measurements performed by its instruments and sensors, is supporting the project in optimizing PROSPECT operations concepts and in defining the criteria for PROSPECT-compatible landing sites in high-latitude lunar polar areas.

Next Steps: With Intuitive Machines in place work is now ramping up to prepare the integration of PROSPECT onboard the Nova-C platform, and to plan the operations of the package as part of the IM-4 mission.

On the development side, assembly and testing of both the Qualification and Flight Model hardware is under way. An important and urgent task now is to mature the overall concept of operations, and the associated ground segment capabilities, which can fulfil both the nominal operations plan and provide the necessary flexibility to react to events in a short timeframe.

PROSPECT will be a unique opportunity to obtain in-situ measurement data on the nature, abundance and sources of volatiles at the lunar south pole including in the subsurface, which can be exploited alongside those of other lunar polar explorers planned in this timeframe, and to provide answers to key scientific questions on the lunar polar environment.

References:

- [1] Fisackerly R. et al. (2021) GLEX-21-2.4.2 (61814), [2] Trautner R. et al (2024) *Frontiers in Space Technologies* Vol. 5, 2673-5075 [3] Heather D. et al. (2026) *European Lunar Symposium*.